

Study of visible light communication System based on Laser LED and Perovskite Photodetector

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Abstract

This project presents the development of an innovative Visible light communication (VLC) system that utilizes a laser LED (420 nm wavelength) and perovskite photodetector for high-speed data transmission. Testing was done under controlled laboratory conditions at room temperature with a 5W, 420 nm LED laser transmitter, 5W amplifier, and 2W speaker system for audio output verification. The system demonstrates good performance characteristics under optimal conditions, while the perovskite photodetector shows superior detection capabilities with low response times below 5 ms. Through series of performance analysis, the system shows strong signal processing and reliable audio transmission capabilities. This research benefits in optical wireless communication technology, offering promising applications in indoor communications, smart buildings, and environments where radio frequency communication is restricted or undesirable. The system's integration of perovskite photodetectors also offers enhanced performance characteristics, making it suitable for next-generation optical communication networks.

Keywords: visible light communication, laser LED, perovskite, CsPbBr₃.

1. Introduction

The exponential growth in wireless data traffic and the increasing demand for high-speed connectivity, have led to significant challenges in traditional radio frequency (RF) communication systems. The limited available RF spectrum with issues of electromagnetic interference and security concerns, has shown the need for exploration of alternative communication technologies. Light Fidelity (LiFi), first introduced by German physicist Harald Haas in 2011 TED (Technology, Entertainment, Design) Global Talk on Visible Light Communication, has emerged as a promising solution that uses visible light for data transmission, offering an alternative opportunity for high-speed wireless communication with highest security [1]. Current traditional wireless communication systems face several critical limitations such as spectrum scarcity in the RF domain, increasing interference in densely populated areas, and security vulnerabilities due to signal penetration through walls. The global LiFi market is experiencing dramatic growth, with projections indicating an increase from USD 656.12 million in 2024 to approximately USD 40,514.95 million by 2034, demonstrating a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 51.03% [2]. This growth reflects the increasing recognition of LiFi's potential to address current communication challenges. Recent research has also explored laser-based LiFi as a means to surpass the data rate constraints of both 5G and traditional LED-based LiFi systems. Using commercial high-power laser diodes and basic on-off keying modulation, data transmission speeds of 4 Gbit/s have been demonstrated, with even higher rates achievable through advanced modulation techniques [3].

Our research focuses on the integration of CsPbBr₃ perovskite photodetectors in VLC systems, an emerging semiconductor material and representing a significant advancement in optical communication technology with a low-power laser LED as the transmission source. CsPbBr₃ perovskite offers several distinctive advantages such as direct and tunable band gap for efficient light absorption, high carrier mobility compared to conventional materials, and cost-effective solution-based fabrication processes. Moreover, CsPbBr₃ perovskite with a bandgap of 2.4 eV has suitable response spectrum to light propagation and short absorption cut-off wavelength at 530 nm can reduce the noise and interference current from long-wavelength radiation, which gives CsPbBr₃ perovskite PDs more advantages than conventional silicon-based PDs [4-6].

2. Experiment section

Perovskite film by thermal evaporation process

CsBr and PbBr₂ powder in DMSO was mixed with an ultrasonic bath for 30 min to receive yellow powder. The powder was centrifuged, dried, and put directly onto a tungsten heating boat (3 mg). The substrate was placed at a distance of 6 cm from the heating boat. A quartz crystal monitor monitored the evaporation rate (deposition speed, ~ 30 nm/s) near the substrate, calibrated by the ratio of actual film thickness to deposition time. The temperature of the heating boat is about 650 °C, and the working pressure at 10⁻⁴ torr.

Characterization:

The surface and cross-section morphologies of FTO/perovskite multilayers were analyzed via scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL). The current–voltage characteristics of the devices were obtained by applying an external bias voltage to the device and measuring the generated photocurrent with a Keithley

model 4200 digital source meter (Keithley, USA) under illumination from a 405 nm laser source coupled with a pulse power generator. Light intensity was calibrated with a silicon photodiode.

Visible light communication System Setup:

The working mechanism of Li-Fi is straightforward. On one end of the system is a laser LED transmitter, which acts as the light source, which functions as a light sensor. Data fed into the LED transmitter is encoded into light signals. This is achieved by modulating the flickering rate of the LEDs. In another end, the photodetector is used to convert the light to electrical signal. This simple yet efficient mechanism allows Li-Fi to transmit data in light form effectively, making it a promising alternative to traditional wireless communication systems.

3. Results and discussion

Figure 1. Vacuum deposition setup and CsPbBr₃ films on FTO and Pt interdigitated electrodes.

The CsPbBr₃ photosensitive layer was deposited by vacuum evaporation using CsPbBr₃ powder, as illustrated in Figure 1. The resulting film is light yellow, uniform, and exhibits green photoluminescence under excitation light (~420 nm). The chemical composition and crystal structure are critical factors influencing its optoelectronic properties.

Figure 2 shows the surface morphology and phase of the CsPbBr₃ powder and film samples fabricated by vacuum evaporation. As observed in Figures 2(a) and 2(b), both the film and powder samples exhibit characteristic peaks of cubic-phase CsPbBr₃ (PDF#73-2478), with diffraction peaks corresponding to the (100), (110), (200), (210), and (211) crystal planes in the 2θ range of 10° to 40°. The lattice parameters are $a = 8.244(3) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 11.73510(5) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 8.19820(6) \text{ \AA}$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$, and $V = 793.128058 \text{ \AA}^3$. No significant secondary phases are observed. The SEM images of the sample surfaces (Figures 2(c) and 2(d)) show that the vacuum-deposited film consists of densely packed nanoparticles with sizes ranging from 100 to 300 nm, without noticeable voids. Figures 3(a) and 3(b) show that the fabricated film has a thickness of approximately 500 nm and a Cs:Pb:Br elemental ratio of ~1:1:3. Based on the XRD and EDS results, it can be confirmed that the fabricated film is a single-phase CsPbBr₃ material.

Figure 2. (a), (b) X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns and (c), (d) SEM images of the CsPbBr₃ powder and film samples, respectively.

Figure 3. (a) Cross-sectional SEM image and (b) EDS spectrum of the CsPbBr₃ film fabricated by vacuum evaporation.

Figure 4. (a) Photoluminescence and UV-vis absorption spectra of the CsPbBr₃ film fabricated by vacuum evaporation, and (b) Tauc plot of the film derived from the UV-vis absorption spectrum.

The optical properties of the film were characterized by absorption and photoluminescence measurements. As shown in Figure 4(a), the film absorbs light in the wavelength region below 510 nm and emits green light with a peak at 515 nm and a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of approximately 25 nm. The optical bandgap of the film, determined from the Tauc plot (Figure 4(b)), is estimated to be around 2.38 eV.

When light is incident on the CsPbBr₃ material, photons excite electrons in the crystal lattice, causing them to transition from the valence band to the conduction band. This results in an increase in the material's electrical conductivity and a corresponding decrease in resistance. Conversely, under lower light intensity, fewer electrons are excited, leading to reduced conductivity and increased resistance. The photosensitive resistance of CsPbBr₃ depends on the intensity and wavelength of the incident light, as well as the quality and thickness of the perovskite film. To characterize the photoresponse properties, a 420 nm laser diode was used as the light source to excite

the CsPbBr₃ photosensitive layer. The power intensity of the light source was measured to be 0.1 mW/cm². Under illumination, photo-generated current can be produced through the photoconductive effect, and the relationship between photocurrent and voltage was recorded using a Keithley 4200 system.

where R is the responsivity, J_d is the dark current density, and q is the elementary charge.

The photodetection performance of the CsPbBr₃-based photodetector is illustrated in Figure 5, demonstrating its sensitivity and stability under various operating

Figure 5. Photodetection performance of the CsPbBr₃-based photodetector. (a) Time-dependent photocurrent response under different light intensities (0.1–1 mW/cm²) at an applied bias of 2 V. (b) Log–log plot of photocurrent (I) versus light intensity (P), (c) Photocurrent–voltage (I – V) characteristics under constant light intensity (1 mW/cm²), (d) Responsivity (A/W) as a function of light intensity at 5 V bias, (e) Specific detectivity (Jones) versus light intensity at 5 V bias.

The photoresponse curve of the photodetector under periodic on/off illumination (0.2 Hz) at zero external bias voltage is shown in the figure 5. The on/off current ratio (I_{on}/I_{off}) was determined to be as high as $\sim 1 \times 10^{-5}$, which is among the best values reported to date. The responsivity and detectivity are key intermediate parameters used to evaluate the performance of the photodetector.

They are defined by the following equations:

$$R = \frac{J_{Ph}}{L_{Light}}$$

where J_{Ph} is the photocurrent density and L_{Light} is the incident light intensity. The responsivity reflects the device's quantum efficiency, i.e., its ability to convert photons into electron–hole pairs.

In addition to responsivity, detectivity is a crucial figure of merit that indicates the device's ability to detect weak optical signals. It is calculated using the equation:

$$D = \frac{R}{\sqrt{2qJ_d}}$$

conditions. As shown in Figure 5 (a), the time-dependent photocurrent response under different light intensities (ranging from 0.1 to 1 mW/cm²) at a bias voltage of 2 V reveals a clear and repeatable on/off switching behavior, indicating good photoresponsivity and reversibility. The log–log plot in Figure 5 (b) presents the relationship between photocurrent and incident light intensity, which follows a power-law behavior with an exponent (β) of 0.87. This value is close to 1 mean that the photoresponse behavior is linear. Figure 5 (c) displays the current–voltage (I – V) characteristics under a constant illumination of 1 mW/cm², showing a monotonic increase in photocurrent with applied voltage, which reflects efficient carrier extraction under an external electric field. Additionally, Figures 5 (d) and (e) show the responsivity and specific detectivity as functions of light intensity at a fixed bias of 5 V. Both parameters exhibit a decreasing trend with increasing light intensity, likely due to the saturation of trap states and increased recombination at higher excitation levels. These results highlight the potential of CsPbBr₃ films for use in photodetectors.

Figure 6(a) Time-dependent photocurrent response of the CsPbBr₃ photodetector. (b) Normalized rise time response and (c) normalized decay time response of the device.

The photoresponse speed is one of the key indicators for evaluating the performance of a photodetector. It is defined as the time required for the signal to rise from 10% to 90% of its maximum value (and vice versa during decay). Figure 6(a) shows the photoresponse curve of the device, indicating a response time of less than 5 ms, which is limited by the resolution of the measurement system (Keithley 4200 SCS).

Figure 7. Basic visible light communication experiment setup.

Figure 7 illustrates a simple optical audio transmission system in which an audio signal is transmitted via a laser beam. The process begins with an audio signal generated from a computer, which is then fed into a modulator to drive the laser. The laser emits light rays modulated by the audio signal, which travel through a medium (typically air) and reach a photodetector. The photodetector converts the received light signal back into an electrical audio signal. This signal is then sent to an audio amplifier to boost its strength before being output through a speaker. This setup demonstrates the principle of free-space optical communication for transmitting sound using light.

4. Conclusion

This study successfully implements and validates a visible light audio communication system using a

perovskite-based photodetector and a 420 nm, 5-watt laser LED light source. The experimental setup demonstrates that visible light can be effectively employed to transmit audio signals in real time, achieving a secure and interference-free communication channel. The perovskite photodetector exhibited promising performance, with a measured responsivity of 4 A/W, the rising and falling time is below 5 ms, confirming its sensitivity and practical suitability for visible light communication applications.

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